

GreenDIGIT

Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures

Deliverable D8.2 First Policy Recommendations

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Executive Summary

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are increasingly expected to demonstrate environmental responsibility alongside scientific excellence. This deliverable provides a first set of policy recommendations for greening digital RIs, based on regulatory review, sectoral analysis, and the intermediate results of the GreenDIGIT project.

Current Policy Landscape and Gaps

Digital RIs operate within a complex policy environment shaped by EU sustainability directives, global climate goals, and industry standards. Key regulations such as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), and Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE Directive) provide a strong foundation for energy efficiency, circularity, and emissions reporting. However, policy gaps remain: most regulations do not fully address RI-specific needs, especially around tailored metrics, procurement, e-waste, renewable energy obligations, and lifecycle integration.

Survey Insights from the RI Community

GreenDIGIT surveyed digital RIs to assess their current sustainability practices and needs. While most are aware of environmental challenges, they remain in early stages of internal policy development. The survey identified a strong need for guidance, practical tools, policy templates, and harmonized evaluation metrics. A lack of dedicated roles and structured governance was also observed, as well as interest in sharing best practices and aligning with EU policy frameworks.

Tools and Frameworks for Internal RI Policy

To meet these needs, GreenDIGIT developed both an Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and a Self-Assessment Questionnaire. These tools enable RIs to benchmark their environmental maturity, define improvement targets, and develop action plans aligned with EU frameworks such as the CSRD, EED, and European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). The questionnaire also supports traceability and audit readiness, helping RIs align internal policies with broader policy expectations.

Recommendations Across Governance Levels

The deliverable outlines detailed policy recommendations across three complementary levels:

- **Digital RIs**, who need support in designing internal sustainability policies and embedding environmental governance;
- **European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure (ESFRI) and Horizon Europe**, who play a strategic role in shaping funding frameworks, sector benchmarks, and cross-infrastructure learning;
- **Policymakers**, who are positioned to enable structural change through targeted regulation, harmonization, and incentives.

Each actor has a unique role to play in supporting sustainability goals through actions such as assessing current practices, defining policy objectives, monitoring progress, creating incentives, sharing knowledge, and considering potential binding pathways.

The matrix on the next page (Table 1) provides a high-level synthesis of these stakeholder roles and action areas across six categories: Assess, Define, Incentivize, Monitor, Share, and Consider binding pathways.

It was developed based on the findings and needs identified in each category of the analysis, in order to provide a comprehensive view. The matrix shows that while the actions to be taken are similar in nature across all stakeholder groups, they must be addressed at different levels depending on each actor's responsibility, influence, and operational scope. Each topic introduced in the matrix is further developed and substantiated in the deliverable.

This deliverable presents a first set of policy recommendations developed within GreenDIGIT. These recommendations are intentionally non-binding at this stage, as their primary objective is to identify and structure an initial set of proposals, serve as a basis for discussion with key stakeholders (including ESFRI and related initiatives), and assess their relevance, applicability, and potential level of support across the RI ecosystem. This is important as we should carefully assess the implications of these first set of policies, with respect to complexity, regulation costs and other metrics if possible.

In this perspective, the recommendations matrix includes a specific action category (“Consider binding pathways”), which explores potential trajectories through which voluntary practices and identified best practices could progressively be embedded into more structural or binding frameworks, without anticipating specific regulatory or governance outcomes. A second step, planned in the next phase of GreenDIGIT (WP9), will build on stakeholder feedback to further refine, validate and strengthen these recommendations, with the objective that they could eventually be endorsed and supported by the relevant communities.

These preliminary recommendations will now be discussed and tested with key stakeholder groups during the next phase of the project - WP9 “Policy recommendations, roadmap and assessment guide for green digital RIs” - which will run over 15 months and will lead to the final set of policy recommendations.

Table 1: Synthesis of first policy recommendations to Digital RIs, ESFRI and Horizon Europe, and Policymakers

Stakeholders	Targets	Actions					
		Assess	Define	Incentivize	Monitor	Share	Consider binding pathways
RIs	Internal policies	GreenDIGIT methodology & Self-assessment Questionnaire	Internal policies with KPIs & Objectives	Environmental policy champions	Qualitative evidence, supporting traceability, and readiness for audits	Good practices Lessons learnt Training Pilot projects	Consider potential integration into mandatory internal procedures
ESFRI & HE	RI sustainable framework	Cross RI benchmark Portfolio evaluation Benchmark sectoral progress	Sustainability metrics	Sustainability as a funding criteria Support GreenRI certification scheme Fund sustainability enabling research	Federated monitoring and reporting infrastructure	Cross-RIs knowledge exchange Circular Economy and Sustainable Procurement Principles	Consider potential integration of sustainability metrics into ESFRI monitoring, evaluation and governance processes
Policy makers	Future regulations	Understand readiness level of RIs and needs Assess policy instruments	Harmonized sustainability metrics and standards	Certification scheme Green Innovation in RIs Sustainability criteria in Research Funding	Standardized environmental monitoring and reporting	Collaborative approaches: research–industry engagement; cross-sector policy best practices; international cooperation on sustainable RIs	Consider potential translation of best practices into future policy instruments

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
CNDCP	Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CUE	Carbon Usage Effectiveness
DPI	UN Digital Public Infrastructure
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EMS	Environmental Management System
EnMS	Energy Management Systems
EOSC	European Open Source Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FLOPS	FLoating point Operations Per Second
IoT	Internet of Things
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Lifecycle Assessment
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
RAN	Radio Access Networks
RI	Research Infrastructure
SDG	UN Sustainable Development Goal
VM	Virtual Machine
WEEE	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WUE	Water Usage Effectiveness

1 Introduction

Research Infrastructures (RIs), and in particular digital RIs, are essential pillars of scientific advancement in Europe. As such, their environmental footprint is becoming an increasingly important issue in the context of the European Green Deal [1] and international sustainability commitments. While many RIs have begun to take steps toward improved environmental performance, the regulatory landscape remains complex and fragmented, and sector-specific policy guidance is still emerging.

This deliverable, *D8.2 – First Policy Recommendations*, presents an initial set of strategic and actionable recommendations designed to support the greening of digital RIs. It draws upon a comprehensive review of current policies, regulatory gaps, and operational practices, as well as the results of surveys and assessments carried out within the GreenDIGIT project. This deliverable will serve as input for a broader validation phase to be carried out in WP9, dedicated to refining and finalizing the policy roadmap and recommendations.

The objective is to support internal RI policy development, inform future European and national regulatory frameworks, and provide direction to key actors including ESFRI and Horizon Europe. Special attention is given to tools and methodologies- such as the Environmental Impact Assessment framework and the Self-Assessment Questionnaire- developed within GreenDIGIT to guide the policy dimension of sustainability implementation in line with regulatory expectations and technical realities.

Looking ahead, a key challenge will be to disseminate, incentivize and sustain the adoption of environmental practices across a diverse and evolving RI landscape. Among various approaches, instruments such as sustainability-linked certification schemes may offer useful incentives, provided they are simple and aligned with operational realities and existing frameworks.

2 Assessment of existing policies and regulations, gaps identification

2.1 Overview of current policy landscape

The policy landscape influencing environmental sustainability of digital research infrastructures (RIs) is becoming increasingly robust, driven by international climate and sustainable development commitments and EU regulatory ambitions. At the global level, the **UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)** [2] provide the foundational sustainability objectives that RIs are expected to support. Particularly SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals). Additionally, the **UN Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI)** promotes open, interoperable digital systems to foster exchange of data and services across various sectors. Integrating DPI principles into RI operations can support open data discovery, circularity, and technical implementation to create platforms that facilitate exchange of environmental data, quality assurance, and compliance.

At the European level, the **European Green Deal** [1] provides the overarching framework, aiming for a climate-neutral Europe by 2050. Its goals are operationalized through several key legislative and strategic instruments. The **Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)** and **European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS)** mandate large organizations to disclose sustainability performance, including carbon emissions, energy and water usage, and circularity indicators. This is reinforced by the **EU Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1364**, which introduces reporting obligations for data centres with a minimum IT load of 500 kW, requiring metrics such as Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), Water Usage Effectiveness (WUE), Renewable Energy Factor (REF), and Energy Reuse Factor (ERF).

Sector-specific regulations also play a critical role. The **Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)** establishes binding energy reduction targets, including mandatory energy audits and waste heat recovery for large infrastructures. The **Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)** introduces lifecycle-based sustainability criteria for IT equipment, such as modularity, repairability, and recyclability, while the **Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive** enforces proper collection and recycling of electronic waste. Industry-driven initiatives, such as the **Climate Neutral Data Centre Pact (CNDCP)** and the **EU Code of Conduct for Data Centre Energy Efficiency**, offer voluntary best practices and benchmarks, particularly for energy efficiency, renewable energy use, and water conservation.

2.2 Key policy areas impacting digital RIs

Energy consumption: The EED and Regulation (EU) 2024/1364 require monitoring and reduction of energy use. Voluntary frameworks (e.g. ISO 50001, EN 50600) encourage the use of smart grid integration, workload optimization, and dynamic energy management.

Carbon footprint policies: Carbon footprint policies increasingly require RIs to monitor and disclose their greenhouse gas emissions. Under the CSRD and ESRS, organizations must report Scope 1, 2, and

3 emissions, while metrics like Carbon Usage Effectiveness (CUE) are used to assess the carbon intensity of IT operations. The voluntary Science Based Targets initiative (SBTi) provides a methodology for setting institution-wide carbon reduction goals aligned with the Paris Agreement. Although frameworks like the EU Delegated Regulation 2024/1364 mandate reporting, there are currently no binding emission reduction targets specific to RIs.

Waste management and circular economy: Policies such as the ESPR and WEEE Directive are central to improving IT hardware sustainability. Requirements include extended product lifespans, take-back schemes, modular upgrades, and e-waste tracking. The forthcoming Digital Product Passport (DPP) will also increase transparency across IT supply chains.

Water use: Water usage in cooling systems is regulated via WUE benchmarks in the EU Regulation 2024/1364 and the CNDPC, highlighting the growing importance of water-efficient design and operations, especially in water stressed regions.

2.3 Identified gaps from policies

Despite a growing body of international, European, and national policies regarding environmental sustainability in digital infrastructures, some regulatory and implementation gaps persist, particularly where the general policy frameworks fail to address specific operational realities, technical heterogeneity or resource constraints of RIs. This disconnect may result in fragmented compliance efforts, limited uptake of best practices, and missed opportunities for harmonized sustainability improvements across the research ecosystem.

- **Lack of tailored metrics and benchmarks for RIs:** While PUE, CUE, and WUE are increasingly standardized, few policies provide guidance specific to RI architectures. This limits comparability and sector-specific benchmarking.
- **Sustainable procurement criteria are underdeveloped:** Existing policies lack enforceable green procurement standards adapted to RI contexts. Few guidelines exist on evaluating the embedded environmental impact of IT services or equipment beyond energy efficiency labels.
- **Challenges in e-waste and circularity implementation:** Although the WEEE Directive mandates proper treatment and recycling of electrical and electronic waste, majority of EU Member States do not meet its collection targets, and only about 40% of collected WEEE is recycled [3]. RIs may lack dedicated infrastructure for refurbishment, secure e-waste disposal, and tracking of asset lifecycles.
- **Limited obligations for renewable energy adoption:** While the CNDPC and EED encourage renewable procurement, binding targets are lacking.
- **Integration of lifecycle assessment (LCA) in policy compliance:** Although LCA is referenced in ESPR and CSRD contexts, it is not yet consistently required for procurement, design, or decommissioning of infrastructure, despite its value in quantifying environmental impacts.

3 Analysis of digital RIs practices and needs concerning policies

GreenDIGIT carried out a survey conducted from March to November 2024 among digital RIs to give a landscape review, and the analysis of identified practices, needs, and gaps within these infrastructures as part of the GreenDIGIT project. This work led to the deliverable D3.1 “RIs Landscape review, best practices analysis and identification of needs within the ESFRI RIs” (November 2024). The key elements of this deliverable, related to policies, are presented below, and all details can be found in D3.1.

3.1 Most RIs remain at an early stage and need support for the transition

A key conclusion of the survey that we conducted, regarding the RIs practices and needs concerning policies is the following:

The results of the survey highlight the **diversity of situations** regarding the environmental impact of digital RIs. While **most are fully aware** of the challenges, and the results show progress, particularly in renewable energy use and energy efficiency, **the majority remain at an early stage, lacking methodologies, policies, and resources to facilitate the transition**. Thanks to the survey, not only was it acknowledged that there is still ample room for improvement (a non-trivial result), but it also became possible to measure its actual worth quantitatively. Existing approaches are often limited to energy consumption and rely on in-house methods that are difficult to integrate into more holistic carbon and waste management practices. However, **a few have already implemented good practices**, which can serve as a valuable resource for others. Sharing and benefiting from these best practices represents a clear call to collaborate to structure future efforts. Finally, it will be essential to discuss with ESFRI what steps should be taken to organize and promote best practices and potentially establish common policies.

3.2 Policy and governance gaps from the RIs point of view

The responses were received from RIs that are at different stages of their implementation. While most of the respondents are in full operation and then have more limited options to introduce environmental sustainability-related aspects into their operation, some respondent RIs are still in design, prototyping or pre-production phases, with significant investments to go into procurements and deployments in the coming years. **Solutions, such as recommendations, policy templates, education, and assessment frameworks, will be therefore required for RIs through their entire lifecycle**. GreenDIGIT will develop solutions through the entire RI lifecycle, and for the maximum adoption, the vocabulary used in these solutions should match the lifecycle definitions of ESFRI in its roadmap 2026 [4].

Figure 1: ESFRI RI lifecycle approach (ESFRI Roadmap 2026 [4])

3.3 Policy and regulatory alignment

A key conclusion of D3.1 is that policy and regulatory alignment is a crucial area for improving sustainability in RIs. Compliance with national, European, and international standards on energy efficiency and sustainability practices offers RIs both challenges and opportunities. By integrating sustainability metrics into evaluation frameworks and exploring the use of sustainability certifications, RIs can demonstrate and communicate environmentally responsible practices in the field.

Incorporation of sustainability metrics: The integration of sustainability metrics remains a key area for development within RIs. Several respondents to the GreenDIGIT survey indicated that their infrastructures currently lack a comprehensive system for tracking and reporting energy efficiency or carbon emissions. However, some respondents reported using specific metrics to track energy efficiency, with PUE being the most common. Other metrics, such as Watts per virtual machine (VM), Watts per graphics processing unit (GPU), or Floating point Operations Per Second (FLOPS) per Watt, are also employed. Some RIs monitor energy consumption on an annual basis, comparing scientific and operational usage. There is a clear opportunity to establish standardized energy monitoring systems, which could be embedded into dashboards or research tools to assist both operators and researchers in reducing energy usage. Energy consumption metrics, such as kilowatt constant draw, can also be used to convert tracked energy usage into approximate carbon emission tonnes. Tracking carbon emissions on an annual basis allows RIs to compare metrics and take actions toward reducing emissions.

Compliance with regulations and certification schemes: Most respondents to the GreenDIGIT survey indicated that compliance with national and European energy standards and regulations is managed by higher-level institutional bodies, such as building infrastructure departments or national nodes. While some RIs reported adhering to energy limits imposed by national regulations, others are in the process of developing policies to address energy consumption and carbon footprint. Certification

schemes aiming to assess and certify sustainability measures pose an additional opportunity to demonstrate compliance and build value for both operators and end users. Encouraging alignment with certifications and performance measurements not only validates ongoing efforts but can also foster a culture of continuous improvement in sustainability management.

4 First recommendations for digital RIs to establish internal policies

4.1 The GreenDIGIT Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Guidelines for RIs

The GreenDIGIT Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Guidelines for RIs, developed as an output of tasks T3.2 and T3.3 and reported on in detail in D3.2 [5], provide a framework for assessing RI environmental sustainability across the RI lifecycle. They provide a theoretical base, which the GreenDIGIT self-assessment questionnaire (presented in Section 4.2) complements as a tool to implement the methodology. This methodology enables RIs to assess their current capability levels, identify goals, and prioritise actions to leverage opportunities and define an action plan for internal policies in an impactful manner.

The guidelines in D3.2 provide a detailed overview of relevant topics for RIs to consider when setting internal policies across the whole lifecycle, which are summarized below.

Concept development: Environmental sustainability should be embedded across the entire lifecycle of RIs, beginning from the earliest planning stages. During the concept development phase, it is essential to define a clear sustainability vision aligned with the EU Green Deal and the goal of net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 [6]. Establishing environmental Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), integrating climate adaptation strategies, and identifying long-term environmental opportunities at this stage creates the foundation for flexibility, accountability, and alignment with policy frameworks.

Design: As the infrastructure enters the design phase, architectural and technical decisions must reflect sustainability objectives in a concrete and measurable way. A modular and layered infrastructure enables targeted optimisations and facilitates energy-aware orchestration, while also supporting long-term adaptability. Design strategies should prioritise low-impact, circular materials, bioclimatic principles, and green ICT procurement standards. Embedding observability into the infrastructure from the outset ensures monitoring readiness, enabling the use of standardised KPIs such as PUE, CUE, and WUE.

Energy and resource efficiency are best achieved through a combination of approaches: reducing overall consumption, sourcing renewable energy, extending product lifecycles, and encouraging reuse. Implementing ISO 50001-compliant energy management systems (EnMSs), designing for natural climate advantages (e.g. passive cooling), and adopting circular practices such as repair policies and modular hardware support long-term operational sustainability. Additionally, federated platforms and shared infrastructures help avoid duplication and scale energy efficiency across the RI ecosystem.

Preparation: The preparation phase translates the strategic vision and sustainability objectives defined in the concept and design stages into an operational action plan. It encompasses securing financing and partnership agreements with explicit consideration of the costs and benefits of environmental impact management, and formalising commitments from stakeholders, suppliers, and service providers. A core outcome of this phase should be the establishment of an environmental policy, in line with relevant standards, that guides both administrative and operational decisions and

is embedded in contractual agreements. Organisational structures and governance arrangements should be set up, supported by management tools and initial baseline measurements for key sustainability indicators. Communication and training plans can also help prepare teams to implement best practices in energy management, procurement, and environmental monitoring. The phase may also include the development and testing of prototypes to validate metrics or technical solutions, ensuring that subsequent implementation is informed by proven, effective approaches. The preparation phase should result in concrete deliverables, including signed agreements, implementation plan, validated governance structures, and where applicable, prototype systems, providing a solid foundation for the subsequent implementation and operation phases.

Implementation: During implementation, services and tools should be designed with flexibility and energy efficiency in mind, enabling the reengineering of workflows and the optimisation of scientific applications. Modular systems are preferred to allow upgrades with minimal environmental disruption. RIs should gather detailed information about their energy infrastructure and apply power grid-aware computing, adjusting consumption based on carbon intensity, price, or the site's energy profile. Real-time monitoring systems should be in place from the outset, supporting transparency and continuous evaluation of sustainability metrics across all layers of the infrastructure.

Operation: During operation, sustainability should be integrated into all routine practices, supported by an observability framework that enables fine-grained optimisation from applications to hardware. Load shifting and job scheduling strategies can align computing tasks with greener grid conditions, reducing carbon intensity without significant performance loss. Training and clear documentation further support the sustainability culture, while evaluation mechanisms ensure that the environmental impact of optimisations is regularly assessed and balanced across the system.

Termination: Finally, termination planning must be recognized as an integral part of the RI lifecycle. Responsible decommissioning involves secure data migration or deletion, recovery and recycling of hardware, and minimisation of residual carbon and material impacts. Designing for disassembly, planning for asset reuse, and addressing long-term community and financial implications ensures a low-impact closure and reinforces the principles of circularity.

4.2 The GreenDIGIT Self-assessment questionnaire

The GreenDIGIT Self-Assessment Questionnaire, developed under Task 8.2, and presented in D8.1 [7] represents a key policy-support tool for RIs aiming to evaluate and enhance their environmental sustainability maturity. The questionnaire complements the theoretical foundation of the methodology (presented in Section 4.1 above) and serves as a practical tool to help RIs implement it. Designed in alignment with EU regulatory frameworks and sectoral best practices, the questionnaire provides a structured mechanism to assess current practices, identify improvement areas, and link RI operations to relevant policy obligations.

4.2.1 Policy-Relevant Features of the Self-Assessment Tool

The self-assessment questionnaire integrates design elements that directly support policy implementation, traceability, and operationalization within RIs. These features ensure the tool is not only evaluative but also actionable and policy-aligned.

- **Thematic Coverage Anchored in Policy Domains**

The questionnaire covers a comprehensive range of themes—including governance, energy and resource efficiency, circularity, digital infrastructure design, and stakeholder engagement—each mapped to relevant EU and international frameworks such as:

- CSRD and ESRS (notably ESRS E1 on climate)
- EED
- ESPR
- WEEE Directive
- ISO 14001, ISO 50001 standards
- CNDPC

- **Structured Capability Levels**

Each evaluation point is supported by clearly defined capability levels (1–3), describing the degree of policy alignment and implementation maturity. These levels reflect policy-relevant milestones—e.g., basic awareness (Level 1), partial implementation (Level 2), and best-practice or regulatory compliance (Level 3). This allows RIs to identify not only operational gaps but also areas of non-alignment with regulatory expectations.

- **Evidence-Based and Auditable Reporting**

The tool prompts respondents to provide qualitative notes and evidence, supporting traceability and facilitating readiness for audits linked to CSRD, Horizon Europe environmental screening, or ESFRI evaluations.

- **Integration with Environmental KPIs and Metrics**

The questionnaire operationalizes key policy metrics—PUE, CUE, WUE, Scope 1–3 emissions, energy reuse and renewable sourcing factors—aligning with EU Regulation 2024/1364 and ISO-based energy/environmental management systems (EMSs). This facilitates performance tracking and policy-driven benchmarking.

- **Strategic Planning and Target-Setting**

The assessment framework encourages RIs to set target capability levels, guiding forward-looking policy planning and investment. This supports the development of internal sustainability roadmaps that are policy-compliant and tailored to the RI’s maturity.

- **Effort-Based Action Planning**

Action plans are generated based on selected effort levels and current vs. target capabilities, guiding policy-relevant interventions in areas such as procurement, waste management, water cooling, stakeholder engagement, and LCA. This links strategic planning with actionable, policy-sensitive steps.

4.2.2 Policy Implications and Use Cases

The outputs of the self-assessment enable RIs and also policymakers to derive strategic insights, support planning, and strengthen compliance. The tool also provides a foundation for institutional dialogue, benchmarking, and informed funding or regulatory decisions.

- **For RI Management:** The questionnaire acts as an internal policy audit tool, allowing RIs to self-evaluate their degree of compliance with emerging legal requirements (e.g., under CSRD or EED) and to guide strategic sustainability initiatives.

- **For ESFRI and Horizon Europe:** The maturity data collected through self-assessments can be aggregated to inform funding decisions, identify policy adoption bottlenecks across RIs, and benchmark sectoral progress toward climate and sustainability goals.
- **For Policymakers:** The questionnaire enables a bottom-up understanding of RI readiness and needs, offering insights into where policy instruments are succeeding or falling short in driving sustainability transformation in the research ecosystem.

4.3 Recommendations to establish internal policies

Based on the methodology and the Self-assessment Questionnaire described in Sections 4.1 and 4.2, this section presents a set of priority recommendations for internal RI policies. These recommendations draw on the Questionnaire’s recommended actions, and we have enriched them with more concrete and context-specific proposals to better address the policy needs identified.

By engaging RI governance bodies, technical teams, and stakeholders in co-creation after completing the survey analysis and self-assessment, these actions will be tailored, practical, and context-sensitive. Most correspond directly to the Questionnaire’s general sustainability targets, while others are detailed adaptations to respond to specific contexts. For example, the recommendation “Assign environmental policy champions” corresponds to the Questionnaire’s broader recommendation “Identify key functions and assign clear responsibilities for environmental sustainability, ensuring that responsibility is not siloed but shared across operational and strategic roles.”

4.3.1 Addressing Early-Stage Maturity and Governance Gaps in Environmental Sustainability

Most digital RIs today remain at an early stage of green sustainability maturity, lacking formal environmental policies, dedicated roles and standardized metrics to track progress. To remedy this:

- **Establish an Environmental Sustainability Steering Committee**
Create a cross-functional body composed of senior management, technical leads and external advisors. This committee will define strategic green targets, oversee policy adoption across departments and meet quarterly to review progress against environmental milestones.
- **Define clear environmental policy objectives**
Translate high-level green goals (for example, net-zero operations by 2035; 50 percent reduction in Scope 1–3 emissions by 2030) into measurable milestones. Align these objectives with recognized standards such as ISO 14001 for environmental management and ISO 50001 for energy management, ensuring consistency with EU Green Deal targets. In doing so, consider referencing the EU Taxonomy framework [8] to ensure that environmental objectives and investments are aligned with scientifically robust criteria for sustainability. This not only enhances credibility but may also facilitate access to sustainable finance.
- **Assign “environmental policy champions”**
Nominate domain-specific champions—such as an Energy Manager, a Circularity Officer and a Green Procurement Lead—who will coordinate implementation of environmental policies, train staff on new procedures and report monthly on green KPIs.

4.3.2 Develop Tailored Metrics and Monitoring for Green Performance

Section 3 highlighted the absence of RI-specific green benchmarks beyond generic PUE, CUE and WUE, limiting comparability and continuous improvement in environmental performance. Recommended actions include:

- **Standardize green energy and carbon metrics**
Equip data centres and labs with Internet of Things (IoT)-enabled meters that feed into a unified green dashboard. Beyond PUE and CUE, introduce workload-level indicators such as “FLOPS per Watt” or “Watts per VM” to capture efficiency at the application layer. Dashboards should update hourly and be accessible to all stakeholders.
- **Integrate LCA for environmental impact**
Embed LCA tools into procurement and decommission workflows so that every new purchase or retirement of equipment triggers an environmental impact calculation. This ensures decisions consider cradle-to-grave impacts and drives selection toward lower-impact options.
- **Publish an annual green sustainability report**
Consolidate all environmental metrics into an externally published report structured around the Greenhouse Gas Protocol’s Scope 1–3 framework. Include a traffic-light system (green, amber, red) to flag areas needing additional focus and to celebrate eco-achievements.

4.3.3 Strengthen Green Procurement and Circularity

The survey revealed underdeveloped green procurement criteria and weak e-waste management infrastructure across many RIs. To close these gaps:

- **Adopt ESPR-compliant green procurement policies**
Revise tender documents to require modular, repairable and energy-labelled hardware. Set minimum requirements for supplier take-back services and extended warranties, incentivizing vendors to design for longevity and ease of repair.
- **Implement take-back and refurbishment schemes**
Partner with certified recyclers and repair centres to collect retired equipment. Track all assets via a DPP that records purchase date, maintenance history and environmental footprint, enabling transparent circularity reporting.
- **Require environmental risk assessments for investments**
For every capital investment above a defined threshold, mandate an environmental risk assessment that evaluates raw-material sourcing, manufacturing impacts and end-of-life scenarios. Include findings in the approval process to ensure alignment with circular-economy principles.

4.3.4 Embed Renewable Energy and Cooling Efficiency

Limited binding obligations for renewable sourcing and water-use efficiency expose RIs to regulatory and reputational risks in green sustainability. Recommended policies include:

- **Set escalating targets for on-site renewable energy**

Commit to generating at least 50 percent of electricity from on-site solar or wind by 2028, rising to 100 percent by 2035. Where on-site generation is infeasible, secure long-term green energy purchase agreements with guarantees of origin.

- **Optimize cooling systems for environmental performance**
Retrofit existing data-hall chillers with closed-loop or liquid-cooling technologies and deploy AI-driven controls that adjust temperature in real time based on workload and ambient conditions, reducing both energy consumption and water withdrawal.
- **Monitor WUE as a green KPI**
Install submeters on all major cooling and process water circuits. Report WUE monthly, set targets to drive year-on-year reductions and benchmark against peer RIs in similar climates.

4.3.5 Foster Stakeholder Engagement and Continuous Improvement in Green Practices

Sustaining momentum in environmental sustainability requires active participation from researchers, operators and funders. To cultivate a green culture:

- **Launch regular green training and awareness programs**
Offer quarterly workshops and e-learning modules on topics such as energy-efficient coding practices, sustainable lab protocols and responsible data management. Measure impact via post-training surveys and track behaviour change over time.
- **Create feedback loops for green innovation**
Host biannual “sustainability cafés”—informal forums where staff can pitch green ideas, discuss challenges and share success stories. Consolidate input into an internal “ideas pipeline” that feeds into policy updates.
- **Implement green pilot projects**
Trial innovations such as carbon-aware workload schedulers that shift compute tasks to off-peak or low-carbon grid periods and digital twin simulations to identify efficiency improvements before physical implementation. Evaluate pilots against predefined return of investment (ROI) and emissions-reduction metrics.

By embedding these detailed green sustainability recommendations into governance structures, metrics systems, procurement processes and engagement activities, each RI will have a clear, step-by-step policy roadmap ready to be drafted into formal documents and piloted immediately following the survey analysis and self-assessment phase.

5 First recommendations for ESFRI and Horizon Europe to establish a RI sustainable framework

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) and Horizon Europe hold strategic positions in driving the transition toward environmentally sustainable RIs, particularly those relying on digital and hybrid systems. As the environmental impact of RIs becomes increasingly visible and regulated, these frameworks must evolve from enablers of scientific excellence to proactive agents of climate responsibility and systemic sustainability.

First and foremost, sustainability must be fully embedded into RI evaluation and funding schemes. The ESFRI Roadmap 2026 introduces “environmental considerations” as a key dimension of scientific and technical assessments. It is also complemented with the Environmental Strategy Questionnaire. Building on this, all Horizon Europe RI calls and ESFRI selection processes should explicitly require the submission of environmental strategies aligned with the ESRS, especially ESRS E1 on climate change mitigation. Compliance with such regulations as ESPR, and the WEEE Directive, that are applied to both design and operation stages. Applicants should be expected to define operational KPIs, such as PUE, CUE, and WUE, and present plans for emissions reduction, climate resilience, and resource optimization throughout the RI lifecycle.

The following recommendations outline key actions that ESFRI and Horizon Europe can adopt to embed sustainability within their governance mechanisms, funding criteria, technical evaluation, and strategic road mapping.

5.1 Integrate Sustainability into RI Evaluation and Funding Criteria

To operationalize sustainability as a core evaluation and planning dimension, ESFRI and Horizon Europe should formally require the integration of environmental strategies into RI proposals. This includes aligning with ESRS E1 (climate change) and tracking lifecycle environmental impacts throughout the RI’s design, implementation, operation, and decommissioning phases.

Recommended actions:

- Require sustainability strategies in RI funding proposals, referencing ESRS-aligned environmental objectives.
- Mandate KPIs, such as PUE, CUE, and WUE.
- Incorporate environmental scoring in proposal evaluations, alongside scientific excellence and socio-economic impact.
- Require projects to commit to energy efficiency and decarbonisation targets consistent with the European Green Deal.

5.2 Support the Development of a GreenRI Certification Framework

To encourage and reward high-performing infrastructures and create sector-wide incentives, ESFRI should pilot a GreenRI Certification scheme. This certification would recognise RIs that adopt best practices in energy efficiency, renewable energy use, circularity, and sustainability reporting.

This voluntary but incentivised certification would build upon international standards such as ISO 14001 (EMSs), ISO 50001 (EnMSs), and EU initiatives such as the CNDPCP. In line with the EU Delegated Regulation 2024/1364, the certification would assess the integration of renewable energy sources,

energy-efficient IT infrastructure, circular economy practices, and transparency in environmental reporting. Horizon Europe and ESFRI should support piloting and recognition of this certification, providing financial and technical support to RIs preparing for adoption.

Recommended actions:

- Develop a certification framework based on ISO 14001 and ISO 50001 standards, incorporating CNDPC principles and EU Delegated Regulation 2024/1364.
- Include certification readiness as a quality indicator in Horizon Europe calls and ESFRI roadmap updates.
- Provide targeted support (e.g. technical assistance or funding) for RI candidates preparing for certification.
- Explore how certification can be linked to project eligibility, funding bonus criteria, or visibility in ESFRI communication.

5.3 Foster Cross-RI Knowledge Exchange and Policy Alignment

In addition to formal mechanisms, knowledge-sharing and collaborative learning are critical. ESFRI should facilitate the systematic exchange of best practices across RIs—through casebooks, workshops, and sustainability community hubs. These exchanges can highlight the practical application of green technologies, such as carbon-aware workload scheduling, AI-driven cooling optimization, and the use of modular and repairable IT systems as prescribed by the ESPR. To support lifecycle transparency, ESFRI should also encourage the adoption of DPPs to track the environmental attributes of procured equipment.

This would support mutual learning and policy coherence among diverse national and disciplinary infrastructures.

Recommended actions:

- Facilitate the development of a shared ESFRI Sustainability Knowledge Hub featuring case studies, templates, and guidance on implementing green technologies.
- Promote the adoption of digital twins and AI-based optimisation for real-time monitoring of energy and resource use.
- Encourage sector-wide use of carbon-aware scheduling, federated learning for edge efficiency, and open Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR)+GREEN data strategies.
- Support working groups focused on harmonising sustainability policies and operational practices across national nodes.

5.4 Mainstream Circular Economy and Sustainable Procurement Principles

To ensure alignment with ESPR and WEEE regulations, ESFRI and Horizon Europe should embed circularity and sustainable procurement requirements across RI strategic frameworks and evaluation procedures. Alignment with circular economy and green procurement directives must also be reflected in ESFRI guidelines. The principles of the ESPR and the WEEE Directive should be translated into evaluation criteria that prioritise low-impact equipment design, refurbishment, and recycling

strategies. ESFRI can encourage this by requiring environmental impact assessments and sustainability risk analyses in project applications, extending from procurement to end-of-life management.

Recommended actions:

- Mandate the procurement of ESPR-compliant IT and lab equipment with verified repairability, modularity, and recyclability.
- Promote LCAs and sustainability metrics through DPPs.
- Evaluate proposals on their strategies for IT reuse, hardware refurbishment, and e-waste minimisation in compliance with WEEE.
- Require lifecycle-based environmental planning for both central and distributed infrastructure components.

5.5 Enable Federated Environmental Monitoring and Reporting

Given the fragmented nature of sustainability data, ESFRI and Horizon Europe should invest in building federated reporting infrastructures. These systems should enable the collection and benchmarking of environmental metrics across national and domain-specific RIs. Where feasible, indicators should align with the CSRD, the ESRS, and the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities to ensure that RIs remain compliant with emerging disclosure obligations.

Recommended actions:

- Develop or endorse federated platforms for RI environmental reporting, enabling alignment with CSRD and ESRS indicators.
- Standardise reporting formats for Scope 1–3 GHG emissions, energy usage, and environmental KPIs across EU-funded RIs.
- Link reporting performance to future funding and compliance incentives.
- Support the use of European Open Source Cloud (EOSC)-compliant metadata frameworks to ensure open and reusable reporting data.

5.6 Fund Sustainability-Enabling Research and Infrastructure Innovation

ESFRI and Horizon Europe should take an active role in funding the development and deployment of enabling green technologies within research environments, that reduce the environmental footprint of experimental research. This includes targeted investments in AI-based resource optimisation, carbon-aware systems, smart energy management, and circular-by-design infrastructure. Dedicated calls should support experimentation in smart energy management, digital twins for sustainability monitoring, low-carbon hardware platforms (such as Advanced RISC Machines (ARM)-based systems), and federated learning architectures that reduce data movement and energy use. These technologies will not only help RIs meet environmental targets but also position them as frontrunners in Europe's sustainable digital transition.

Recommended actions:

- Launch targeted calls for energy-efficient experimentation, digital twins for sustainability, and green hardware prototyping.

- Fund demonstrator projects that showcase cross-layer sustainability (e.g. green cloud-to-edge-to-lab platforms).
- Incentivise the adoption of sustainability-enabling technologies through innovation partnerships between RIs, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME), and industrial ecosystems.
- Promote collaboration between environmental engineers, RI architects, and data scientists to co-design future-ready, low-impact infrastructures.

The suggested actions will provide ESFRI and Horizon Europe to facilitate the adoption of environmental sustainability by European RIs. By aligning policy, funding, evaluation, and innovation with environmental goals, they can ensure that the next generation of RIs contributes meaningfully to Europe's transition to a climate-neutral, resource-responsible, and scientifically excellent research ecosystem.

6 First recommendations for Policymakers to contribute to future regulations

In light of the previous sections and identified needs, a number of priority areas have emerged where policy action could drive significant impact. The following recommendations aim to support the development of future regulations that align with sustainability goals while being tailored to the specificities of RIs.

6.1 Key policy areas for RIs environmental sustainability

Several core themes should be addressed to improve the environmental performance of RIs in a systematic way:

- Sustainable Energy Use and Carbon Neutrality in RIs
- Circular Economy and Waste Management in RIs
- Sustainable Procurement and Resource Efficiency
- Climate Resilience and Adaptation Measures

These areas reflect where RIs can act both internally and through broader systemic change, and where policy can provide both guidance and leverage.

6.2 Legislative and regulatory proposals

Based on the priority areas identified, a number of potential legislative and regulatory measures could be considered to accelerate the transition to Greener RIs:

- Harmonization of Sustainability Standards Across EU and Global RIs
- Integration of Sustainability Criteria in Research Funding
- Incentives for Green Innovation in RIs
- Strengthening Environmental Reporting for RIs

These proposals aim to align incentives, establish common benchmarks, and ensure accountability across different levels of governance.

6.3 Collaborative approaches for policy development

To ensure that future regulations are both feasible and well-adapted to the RI ecosystem, collaborative policy-making should be encouraged:

- Engaging Research Communities and Industry Stakeholders
- Best Practices from Other Policy Sectors
- International Cooperation on Sustainable RIs

Such collaboration can enhance legitimacy, practicality, and global consistency in policy design.

6.4 Potential implementation strategies

Finally, the effectiveness of proposed measures will depend on robust implementation mechanisms. Several avenues should be considered:

- Roadmap for Policy Adoption and Stakeholder Engagement
- Role of National vs. EU-Level Policymaking
- Monitoring and Enforcement Mechanisms

Turning these recommendations into action will require coordinated governance, shared accountability across institutions, and structured monitoring to guide progress.

6.5 First analysis of a possible GreenRI certification

Certification schemes can be effective tools to incentivise good practices, provide transparency, as well as ensure and value compliance with regulatory requirements. In the context of environmental sustainability, certifications can offer a structured way to track progress, align with policy goals, and demonstrate accountability to policymakers, organisational stakeholders, and the public. For RIs, a tailored sustainability certification would help bridge the gap between high-level policy objectives and the operational realities of technical and scientific environments.

Building on the environmental impact assessment methodology and self-assessment questionnaire developed in GreenDIGIT deliverables D3.2 and D8.1, the project recommends the development of a **GreenRI certification scheme**. This could offer a harmonised framework to assess, prioritise, monitor, and audit actions, and eventually certify the environmental sustainability of RIs across their operations. The certification process would build on the lifecycle-based assessment framework and sustainability KPIs already outlined in the project and could be structured to accommodate different scales and types of infrastructures. Key elements may include a capability assessment, performance thresholds for core sustainability indicators (such as PUE, CUE, WUE, renewable energy use, and waste handling), and documentation requirements for internal policies, training, and governance structures.

Work on the GreenRI certification baseline will continue beyond project month 18 within Work Package 9 (Policy recommendations, roadmap and assessment guide for green digital RIs), specifically under Task 9.3 (Assessment and Certification Baseline). This task will build upon the assessment framework outlined in D3.2 and D8.1 and the first policy recommendations from the current deliverable D8.2 to translate recommendations into actionable certification components. Importantly, Task 9.3 plans to engage with existing standardisation bodies and green certification organisations to ensure that the proposed GreenRI certification will be interoperable with established audit schemes and recognised by the broader sustainability and research communities. The resulting baseline will lay the foundation for a formal certification path, enabling stakeholders to adopt and pursue sustainability goals in a structured and credible way.

7 Conclusion

The transition toward sustainable digital Research Infrastructures is no longer a question of principle - it is a practical necessity. As this deliverable has shown, there is a growing ecosystem of relevant policies and best practices, but significant gaps persist. Many RIs remain at an early stage of maturity, and would benefit from tailored support, coherent policy frameworks, and clear, measurable guidance.

The recommendations outlined in this report are intended to serve as a first step toward a more structured, harmonised, and operational approach to environmental sustainability in RIs. They address needs at multiple levels: internal policy development within RIs, strategic alignment through ESFRI and Horizon Europe, and future-oriented regulatory design by policymakers. The Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and the Self-Assessment Questionnaire developed within GreenDIGIT provide a solid foundation for supporting the policy aspects of this transition, offering structured guidance for both evaluation and planning.

Some practical policy examples for digital RIs are provided in the Appendices. These examples include the key components needed to reflect the recommendations outlined in this deliverable. They offer a useful starting point and can serve as templates for RIs to develop their own policies, adapted to their specific research domain, digital infrastructure implementation and operation, research practices, and interactions with stakeholders and funding bodies. The provided templates will also feed into further developments in WP9.

Looking forward, ensuring widespread adoption of sustainable practices will also require appropriate incentives, adapted to the diversity of infrastructures and their operational constraints. Among possible mechanisms, sustainability-related certification schemes could offer one lever, provided they are developed in coordination with existing standards and community needs. Ultimately, long-term progress will depend on continued collaboration, mutual learning and cross-level policy coherence while mitigating the complexity that such process can add.

The next months of the project, under WP9, will be dedicated to engaging stakeholders around these recommendations and translating them into a final, collectively validated policy roadmap and guidance framework.

References

- [1] European Commission, The European Green Deal. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- [2] United Nations, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Available: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- [3] European Commission, Directorate-General for Environment. Circular Economy: New evaluation looks at how to improve WEEE Directive. Available: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/new-evaluation-looks-how-improve-weee-directive-2025-07-02_en
- [4] ESFRI, Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures, Roadmap 2026, Public Guide, 8th October 2024. Available: https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_Roadmap2026_Public%20Guide_approved_FINAL.pdf
- [5] GreenDIGIT deliverable D3.2 Environmental Impact Assessment Methodology and Guidelines for RIs. Available: <https://greendigit-project.eu/deliverables/>
- [6] United Nations, NetZero. Available: <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/net-zero-coalition>
- [7] GreenDIGIT deliverable D8.1 Self-assessment questionnaire. Available: <https://greendigit-project.eu/deliverables/> The excel file of the questionnaire can be downloaded using the following link: <https://uva.data.surfsara.nl/index.php/s/pJxHsdeakKQfL70> and password GreenDIGITD81Questionnaire!
- [8] EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities. Available: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en

Appendix A. Typical policy elements for Digital RI and data centre

Note: This section provides a reference to the main components which are advised to be reflected in the RI environmental sustainability and can be used as a guidance for defining the practical policy document taking into account the specific scientific domain supported by the policy, organisational structure and national/local regulation.

An **environmental sustainability policy for digital RIs** is a strategic document designed to reduce the environmental impact of operations while maintaining high research performance. It focuses on energy efficiency, carbon reduction, and resource management across digital services, such as data storage, computing, and networking.

By applying this policy, the digital RI can align its operations with **global sustainability standards**, reduce its carbon footprint, and position itself as a leader in the environmentally responsible RI.

Key Components of an Environmental Sustainability Policy for digital RIs

1. Policy Objectives

Defines the overarching goals of the policy to guide operations and align with global and regional sustainability initiatives. (Example)

- Achieve **net-zero carbon emissions** by a specific target year.
- Optimise the energy efficiency of computing and data storage systems.
- Promote responsible data management and lifecycle practices.
- Ensure compliance with international standards and EU sustainability frameworks (e.g., EU Green Deal, ESRS).

2. Governance and Accountability

Establishes governance and accountability structures for implementing and monitoring sustainability goals.

- Designation of a **Sustainability Steering Committee** to oversee initiatives.
- Alignment with **ISO 14001 (EMSs)** and **ISO 50001 (EnMSs)**.
- Regular sustainability audits and reporting (e.g., annual Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions tracking).

3. Energy Efficiency and Carbon Reduction

Outlines strategies to minimise energy use and carbon footprint in computing and operations.

- Transition to **carbon-neutral energy sources**, such as renewables (solar, wind, hydro).
- **Dynamic resource scaling** for cloud services and computational tasks to avoid over-provisioning.
- Optimisation of cooling systems using **liquid cooling, air economisers, and AI-driven cooling management**.
- Adoption of **energy-efficient computing hardware**, such as ARM processors or hardware accelerators.

4. Monitoring, Metrics, and Continuous Improvement

Focuses on real-time monitoring, setting performance metrics, and evolving the policy over time.

- Use of **IoT sensors and AI-powered analytics** for monitoring energy and resource use.
- Establishing KPIs such as **PUE, WUE**, and carbon intensity per computation.
- Regular reviews to align with new technological advancements and regulations.

5. Sustainable Data Management

Focuses on reducing the environmental impact of data storage and processing.

- Implementation of **tiered storage** solutions for active, warm, and cold data, minimizing active power usage.
- Use of **data deduplication, compression, and lifecycle management** to limit unnecessary storage.
- Promotion of **FAIR and GREEN data principles** (e.g., energy-efficient storage of reusable datasets).
- Data archiving and migration to **energy-efficient cloud infrastructures** (e.g., GAIA-X, EOSC, national storage infrastructures).

6. Low-Carbon Networking and Data Transfers

Minimises the energy used for data movement across distributed infrastructures.

- Deployment of **energy-efficient networking technologies** (e.g., high-efficiency optical switches).
- Optimisation of data transfer protocols to minimise transmission overhead.
- Implementation of **data locality strategies** to process data closer to its source and reduce unnecessary transfers.

7. Renewable Energy Integration

Commits to powering digital infrastructure with low-carbon energy sources.

- Transition to **100% renewable energy** for data centres, cloud platforms, and computational nodes.
- Collaboration with energy providers to ensure renewable energy sourcing.
- On-site generation using solar panels, wind turbines, or hybrid solutions.

8. Circular Economy for Digital Equipment

Addresses lifecycle management of hardware to reduce e-waste and promote sustainable procurement.

- Procurement policies prioritising **Energy Star-certified** and environmentally friendly hardware.
- **Refurbishment, recycling, and reuse programs** for outdated equipment.
- Policies for minimising waste during upgrades or decommissioning.

9. Innovation and Research Practices

Encourages energy-conscious research practices and the adoption of sustainable technologies.

- Incentives for **low-energy computational research workflows** (e.g., energy-efficient AI model training).
- Development of **digital twins** for resource optimisation and energy monitoring.
- Integration of AI/ML to predict and manage resource demand dynamically.

10. Stakeholder Engagement and Training

Focuses on engaging users, researchers, and staff to promote sustainability.

- **Sustainability awareness programs** for researchers using the infrastructure.
- Workshops on **energy-efficient computing practices** and responsible data management.
- User engagement dashboards displaying **real-time carbon and energy metrics**.

11. Compliance and Reporting

Commits to adhering to environmental regulations and ensuring transparency in sustainability efforts.

- **Compliance with EU regulations** such as the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities and Circular Economy Action Plan.
- Mandatory **Scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions reporting** for all digital operations.
- Public release of **annual sustainability reports** summarising achievements and challenges.

Summary of Policy Components

Area	Focus
Governance and Accountability	Leadership, ISO certifications, sustainability committees.
Energy Efficiency	Renewable energy, dynamic scaling, cooling optimisation.
Data Management	Tiered storage, FAIR principles, energy-aware data transfer.
Circular Economy	Hardware reuse, sustainable procurement, e-waste reduction.
Low-Carbon Networking	Energy-efficient networking and data transfer protocols.
Innovation	AI for energy management, digital twins, low-carbon workflows.
Stakeholder Engagement	Researcher training, sustainability dashboards, real-time metrics.
Compliance	Scope 1, 2, 3 emissions reporting, EU Green Deal alignment.

ADDITIONAL/Optional:

The policy document can also provide a Roadmap or Policy implementation stages.

Appendix B. Typical policy for Example RI on Experimental Research on Digital Infrastructure Technologies

Overview:

This hypothetical RI focuses on the **entire continuum of digital technologies: Radio Access Networks (RAN), IoT, Edge Computing, Cloud Computing, and Distributed Storage for Research Data**. Given its focus, the RI must prioritise energy-efficient designs, low-carbon operations, and reduced environmental impact across its components.

1. Governance and Strategic Sustainability Framework

Goal: Establish governance mechanisms that prioritise sustainability and align with EU Green Deal objectives.

Recommendations:

- 1. Adopt an Environmental Policy Framework:**
 - Align with **ISO 14001 (Environmental Management)** and **ISO 50001 (Energy Management)** standards.
 - Set clear **carbon neutrality targets** (e.g., net-zero emissions by 2035).
 - Publish **annual sustainability impact reports** detailing energy use, emissions, and progress toward sustainability goals.
- 2. Create a Sustainability Steering Committee:**
 - Oversee energy and environmental initiatives across RAN, IoT, edge, and cloud infrastructure.
 - Develop sustainability KPIs (e.g., energy consumption per experiment, carbon intensity of data processing).
- 3. Integrate LCAs:**
 - Conduct LCAs for all physical and digital components, including RAN equipment, edge servers, and cloud infrastructure, to identify hotspots in environmental impact.

2. Energy Efficiency in RANs

Goal: Reduce the energy intensity of experimental RAN deployments.

Recommendations:

- 1. Adopt Energy-Efficient RAN Designs:**
 - Use **massive Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) antennas** optimised for energy efficiency.
 - Deploy **AI-driven power management** to dynamically adjust base station power based on traffic demand.
- 2. Implement Sleep Mode Technologies:**
 - Equip base stations with **sleep mode capabilities** to reduce power consumption during low-traffic periods.
- 3. Use Renewable Energy for Base Stations:**
 - Install **solar panels or small wind turbines** to power remote or experimental base stations.
 - Utilise **battery storage systems** for backup power needs.

3. IoT and Edge Computing Energy Optimisation

Goal: Minimise the energy footprint of IoT and edge devices while maintaining performance.

Recommendations:

1. **Adopt Low-Power IoT Protocols:**
 - Use energy-efficient protocols such as **LoRaWAN**, **SigBee**, or **BLE** for IoT data transmission.
 - Employ **adaptive data sampling** to reduce the frequency of transmissions.
2. **Energy-Efficient Edge Devices:**
 - Deploy **ARM-based edge processors** known for low power consumption.
 - Use **liquid cooling solutions** for energy-intensive edge servers.
3. **Enable Federated Learning at the Edge:**
 - Train machine learning models locally on edge devices to reduce data transmission energy.
4. **Leverage Renewable Energy:**
 - Equip edge locations with **local solar arrays** or other renewable energy sources to minimise reliance on the grid.

4. Sustainable Cloud Computing Practices

Goal: Optimise energy use in cloud infrastructure while supporting high-performance experimentation.

Recommendations:

1. **Carbon-Aware Workload Scheduling:**
 - Schedule computational tasks to run when renewable energy is abundant (e.g., during peak solar or wind generation).
 - Integrate **carbon intensity APIs** to dynamically allocate workloads to green data centres.
2. **Green Data Centers:**
 - Design cloud data centres with **PUE <1.3**.
 - Utilise **heat recovery systems** to repurpose waste heat for district heating.
3. **Energy-Efficient Virtualisation:**
 - Use lightweight **containerised workloads** (e.g., Docker, Kubernetes) instead of traditional VMs to reduce resource overhead.
4. **Dynamic Resource Scaling:**
 - Implement **auto-scaling algorithms** to allocate computing resources dynamically based on real-time demand.

5. Distributed Storage for Research Data

Goal: Minimise the environmental impact of distributed storage systems used for experimental research data.

Recommendations:

1. **Tiered Storage Solutions:**
 - Adopt **cold storage** for archival data to reduce energy use (e.g., tape storage).
 - Use high-performance **non-volatile memory express solid state drives (NVMe SSDs)** for frequently accessed data while optimising read/write operations.
2. **Data Compression and Deduplication:**

- Apply advanced compression techniques and deduplication to reduce storage capacity requirements.
- 3. **Energy-Aware Data Replication:**
 - Limit unnecessary data replication by using **geo-distributed storage policies** optimized for energy efficiency.
- 4. **Sustainable Data Centres:**
 - Deploy **distributed storage nodes** in renewable-energy-powered data centres.
 - Incorporate **modular designs** to upgrade hardware without replacing entire systems.

6. Cross-Continuum Sustainability Initiatives

Goal: Establish unified sustainability practices across the RAN-IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum.

Recommendations:

1. **Unified Energy Monitoring Platform:**
 - Implement an **IoT-enabled monitoring system** to measure energy consumption and emissions across the entire continuum in real-time.
2. **Digital Twin for Energy Optimisation:**
 - Create a **digital twin** of the RI to simulate and optimise energy consumption across RAN, IoT, edge, and cloud components.
3. **AI for Predictive Maintenance:**
 - Use AI models to predict maintenance needs and optimise the operation of RAN towers, edge servers, and data centres, reducing energy waste.
4. **Lifecycle Policy for Hardware:**
 - Develop policies to **reuse, refurbish, or recycle hardware** across the continuum, ensuring compliance with the **Circular Economy Action Plan**.

7. Researcher Engagement and Awareness

Goal: Foster a culture of sustainability among researchers and stakeholders.

Recommendations:

1. **Sustainability Training for Researchers:**
 - Offer workshops on **energy-efficient experimentation** and sustainable research practices.
 - Provide training on **FAIR principles** to promote efficient data management.
2. **Green Research Grants:**
 - Incentivise researchers to design experiments with **low-carbon footprints** by offering additional funding or rewards for green practices.
3. **User Feedback Loop:**
 - Collect feedback from researchers to identify and address inefficiencies in the RI.

8. Policy and Funding Integration

Goal: Align RI operations with sustainability-focused policies and ensure funding eligibility.

Recommendations:

1. **Align with EU Green Deal:**
 - Incorporate **ESRS** into sustainability metrics.
 - Ensure compliance with **Horizon Europe sustainability guidelines**.
2. **Carbon Credits and Offsets:**

- Purchase carbon credits to offset emissions where reductions are not immediately feasible.
 - Invest in local renewable energy or reforestation projects to balance emissions.
3. **Sustainability Reporting:**
- Publish an annual **Sustainability Performance Report**, tracking progress toward energy efficiency and emissions reductions.